

Application Tracking System Using Natural Language Processing

Tonsia Treesa Thomas
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
tonsiatreesa@gmail.com

Gloriya Mathew
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
gloriyamathew@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Screening resumes from a large pool is a difficult task, and recruiters waste a lot of time reading through each resume. We can optimize this labor-intensive process of screening countless resumes and make our search process much easier. Using Named Entity Recognition (NER), the task of screening resumes is automated with all the extraneous information discarded, making it simpler for recruiters to examine each resume more thoroughly in less time. The proposed method uses phrase-matching similarity to compare the resume to the job description after the text mining process has been completed. The best candidates for a particular job opening can then be determined using the computed ranking scores. The visual representation of the ranking data is aided by data visualization.

Keywords: SpaCy, phrase-matcher, Named Entity Recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

In the past, recruiters were laboured to spend more time reviewing and comparing hundreds of applications with job requirements under pressure from higher authorities in order to select the best candidate. Fresher's who are in rush to find jobs may apply for positions that are irrelevant, therefore it is important to take the time to review applications in light of the employer's needs. To efficiently narrow down the candidates centered on the job description, a sophisticated resume ranking system is required.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Pradeep Kumar Roy, Sarabjeet Singh Chowdhary, Rocky Bhatiab [1] has a system that can sort a large number of resumes at once. The top candidates can then be sorted in accordance with the job description using Content-based Recommendation, Cosine Similarity, and K-NN to identify the resume that are most comparable to it after classification is complete.

Dr.K.Satheesh, A.Jahnavi, L.Iswarya, K.Ayesha, G.Bhanusekhar, K.Hanisha [2] automates the required entities from the resumes using the Spacy NER model, making the recruiting process quick and efficient also generates a graph that displays the score of each resume.

Chirag Daryania, Gurmeet Singh Chhabrab, Harsh Patelc, Indrajeet Kaur Chhabrad, Ruchi Patele [3] after text mining,

each resume is compared with the job description using a vectorization model and cosine similarity. The best candidates for that particular job vacancy can then be found using the derived ranking scores.

III. APPROACHES TO RESUME PARSING AND RANKING

The system functions in two steps. In the first step, the unstructured text of the resumes is used to retrieve all essential candidate information, like skills, work experience, years of school, certifications, etc.

The algorithm extracts these vital qualification details using natural language processing, after which it summarizes each resume. The evaluator's job is made much easier by eliminating all the extraneous and irrelevant information so that he can easily review the condensed form and evaluate the candidate's skills.

In the second stage, rank the resumes based on how closely their contents matches to the specified job description. Using a phrase matcher, the document similarity is evaluated to determine which set of resumes is most appropriate for a job position. Finally, a ranked list of candidates are obtained [4].

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The system's major goal is to automate the hiring process in order to lower hiring costs and increase hiring efficiency. This is our proposed system, which enables applicants to upload resumes in PDF format. Our system then evaluates, classifies, and stores these resumes, which simplifies the search process. The algorithm used by the evaluating system, which falls under the umbrella of artificial intelligence, uses natural language processing. It reads the resumes and converts them into text format by comprehending the natural language/format used by the candidate. To narrow down the candidates based on company criteria, the gained knowledge is documented in a knowledge base and compared to the job description [5].

V. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection

To train the model, first produce manually labelled training data of pickle format. Each document is now a separate data item that is labelled. The results are presented in

a form with start and endpoints of each associated entity for each line having a label for that entity.

B. Data Pre-processing

Data reduction, data transformation, and data cleaning are all part of this process. All of this is done to increase the data's effectiveness. To improve the accuracy of our model, the data can be processed, in order for the classification to be accurate.

- Data cleaning - The dataset can be cleaned up by removing the noisy data or the undesirable entries.
- Removing Stop words - The stop words are the ones that appear in texts the most frequently but aren't particularly important. It's to achieve more accuracy to the model.

C. Preparing a customized NER model using SpaCy:

With features including text classification, named entity recognition, tokenization, and parts of speech tagging, the open-source Python framework for sophisticated natural language processing is called SpaCy.

SpaCy recognizes named and numerical entities, which include person, organization, language, event etc.

D. Tool Used - Colab

Colab creates open-source applications, open standards, and interactive computing services. Allows users to create and run any python code through a web browser, making it incredibly suitable for data analysis and machine learning.

It also offers the easiest option to provide powerful GPU resources for the proposed system.

E. Content based candidate recommendation

Using the entities from phase 1 to build a content-based candidate suggestion is the second stage of our proposed system; it suggests the resumes that has the best match to the job description. To determine how similar the contents of the texts are, the system employs phrase-matchers and similarity measures [6].

VI. BUILD MODEL

Information recovery from unstructured resume materials is the first stage. The selection of features comes next. Here, outline the key components of the job specifications as well as the applicant resumes that will be compared during the hiring process [7]. Finally, score the resumes using similarity metrics like phrase-matcher and recommend the top 'N' applicants for the available post..

The system's functioning can be summed up as follows:

- Import the necessary packages:* Here make the necessary imports such as spacy, pickle, random, re, nltk etc.
- Create language pipeline object and NER component:* The first model to be loaded is the blank SpaCy English model. In the following step, we'll develop a function that takes training data as an input. First, we will include NER, or named entity recognition, in the function at the end of the pipeline. Then add our custom labels to NER component by using `ner.add_label` then disable the other components other than NER.
- Next create an optimizer object:* feed this object to the training method as parameter and for each iteration, shuffle the dataset.
- Document and text processing of targeted CV with trained model.*
- After which the processing and tokenization of requirements document is done:* Using NLTK tokenize, the dataset is divided into tokens. Additionally, preprocessing operations including stop word removal, stemming, and lemmatization are performed on the tokenized dataset.
- Save newly trained NER component to the disk:* save it in a directory using `to_disk` command. Later, you can load the model from the directory by passing the directory path to `spacy.load()` function.
- Next pass pattern list for the phrase matcher:* accepts match patterns in the form of Doc objects.

```
from spacy.matcher import PhraseMatcher

nlp = spacy.load("nlp_model")
matcher = PhraseMatcher(nlp.vocab)
# Run nlp.make_doc to create pattern for matching
patterns = [nlp.make_doc(text) for text in requiredskills]
matcher.add("SkillList", patterns)
#inputing target cv text
doc = nlp(targetcvtext.upper())
matches = matcher(doc)

candidateskills=[]
for match_id, start, end in matches:
    span = doc[start:end]
    candidateskills.append(span.text)
candidateskills = [*set(candidateskills)]
```

Figure 1: Code for phrase matching the required skills against skill list of users

- Create a function analyzecv:* analyze the requirements documents and CV inputted from the user and sort the resultant in descending order.
- Evaluation Measures:* example objects have accurate gold-standard annotations to which predictions are compared and the Scorer class computes the evaluation scores of `ents_p`, `ents_r`, `ents_f` for the entity span.

Figure 2: Workflow diagram of the proposed system

VII. RESULTS

Here, the CV name and the candidates skills compared against the skillset required by the company and also their similarity. The output following successful information extraction from resume is shown in Figure 3 below. The employer is then referred to the top-ranked resumes.

Alice Clark CV.pdf
Skills : ['SQL']
Skills Required : [PHP, JAVASCRIPT, ZEND, CODEIGNITER, SYMFONY, HTML5, PHP]
Percentage : 9.090909090909092
Dona CV.pdf
Skills : ['JAVASCRIPT', 'PHP', 'MYSQL', 'CSS']
Skills Required : [PHP, JAVASCRIPT, ZEND, CODEIGNITER, SYMFONY, HTML5, PHP]
Percentage : 36.36363636363637
TONSIA TREESA THOMAS CV.pdf
Skills : ['CODEIGNITER', 'SQL', 'JAVASCRIPT', 'PHP', 'MYSQL', 'CSS']
Skills Required : [PHP, JAVASCRIPT, ZEND, CODEIGNITER, SYMFONY, HTML5, PHP]
Percentage : 54.54545454545454

Figure 3: Final Output

Based on the results, obtained skill set is compared against the job description and the graph based on similarity score is plotted using Matplotlib as follows:

Figure 5: Plotting the results on bar graph

VIII. CONCLUSION

The organizations receive a huge number of applications for each job opening. To overcome the tedious, time-consuming, and resource-wasting procedure of classifying the relevant candidate's CV [8]. The proposed natural language processing based automated model to address this problem by recommending to HR the resumes of qualified candidates based on the job description given [9]. The proposed method consists of two steps: it parses the resumes and then it recommends resumes based on how closely their content corresponds to the job description.

IX. FUTURE SCOPE

For future job openings, the extracted resume data from the applicant's resume can help in automatically constructing user profiles, which can be used to offer suitable positions for job hunters.

X. REFERENCES

- [1] Pradeep Kumar Roy, Sarabjeet Singh Chowdhary, Rocky Bhatia, 2020. "A Machine Learning approach for automation of Resume Recommendation system."
- [2] Dr.K.Satheesh, A.Jahnavi, L.Iswarya, K.Ayesha, G.Bhanusekhar, K.Hanisha, 2020. "Resume Ranking based on Job Description using SpaCy NER model."
- [3] Chirag Daryania, Gurneet Singh Chhabrab, Harsh Patel, Indrajeet Kaur Chhabrab, Ruchi Patele, 2020. "An Automated Resume Screening System using Natural Language Processing and Similarity."
- [4] Satyaki Sanyal, Souvik Hazra, Soumyashree Adhikary, Neelanjana Ghosh, 2017. "Resume Parser with Natural Language Processing."
- [5] Sujit Amin, Nikita Jayakar, M. Kiruthika, Ambarish Gurjar, 2019. "Best Fit Resume Predictor"
- [6] Al-Otaibi, S.T., Ykhlef, M., 2012. "A survey of job recommender systems."
- [7] Farber, F., Weitzel, T., Keim, T., 2003. "An automated recommendation approach to selection in personnel recruitment."
- [8] Amin, S., Jayakar, N., Sunny, S., Babu, P., M. K. and Gurjar, A. 2019. "Web Application for Screening Resume"
- [9] Yi, X., Allan, J., Croft, W.B., 2007. "Matching resumes and jobs based on relevance models"